

Magnetic, Spectral and Thermal Properties of some New Coordination Polymers

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THE resin and polychelates of salicylic acid-urea/
thiourea-formaldehyde/trioxane are reported in
literature^{1,2}. These inspired us to study *o*-hydroxy-
acetophenoneoxime-urea-formaldehyde (*o*-HAcOUF)
resin and its complexes.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade. Dimethylformamide and methanol were used after distillation. *o*-Hydroxyacetophenoneoxime was prepared by condensing *o*-hydroxyacetophenone³ with hydroxylaminehydrochloride in 70% ethanol.

Preparation of resin: A mixture of *o*-HAcO (7.55 g, 0.05 mol), urea (3.0 g, 0.05 mol) and formaldehyde (8.1 ml, 0.1 mol) in the presence of 5% NaOH was heated at 55° for 3 h in a water-bath. The separated brown coloured resin was washed with hot water and dried. The dried resin was soxhlet-extracted with solvent ether to remove unreacted *o*-HAcO-F resin and purified by dissolving in 8% NaOH, reprecipitating by dropwise addition of 1 : 1 (v/v) HCl-water, washed with boiling water and dried.

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Preparation of polymeric complexes: *o*-HAcOUF (1.51 g, 0.01 mol) was dissolved in DMF (100 ml) containing a slight amount of water. To it copper(II) nitrate (1.21 g, 0.005 mol) in DMF (100 ml) was added slowly with constant stirring. A green solid was precipitated out at 6.5 pH when an aqueous saturated solution of sodium acetate was added. The product was digested for sometime on a water-bath. It was filtered and washed with DMF, hot water and dried (60°). The Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II}, VO^{II} and UO₂^{II} complexes were prepared in a similar manner. Metal nitrates were used for the Ni, Co and UO₂ complexes, metal acetates for the Mn and Zn complexes and vanadyl sulphate for VO complex.

For the preparation of the Ti^{IV} complex, metal tetrachloride (1.89 g, 0.01 mol) in CCl₄ (20 ml) was mixed with the ligand dissolved in DMF (3.02 g, 0.02 mol) and the solution was refluxed for about 7 h until the evolution of hydrogen chloride ceased. The Zr^{IV} complex was prepared similarly. The chelates were washed and dried as discussed above. The elemental analyses of the compounds are shown in Table 1.

Elemental analyses, electronic (reflectance) spectra, magnetic and thermal studies were carried out as described earlier⁴.

Results and Discussion

Infrared spectra: The ir band at 2 720 cm⁻¹ in the resin is absent in case of the complexes, which indicates the replacement of hydrogen of phenolic group (2-position) by the metal ions⁵. The lowering of the 1 630 cm⁻¹ (C=O) band of the resin by 10–15 cm⁻¹ in polymeric complexes indicates the coordination of the metal ions through nitrogen of oximino group, and the bands in the region 930–990 cm⁻¹ are due to N–O stretching. The increase

of 930–990 cm⁻¹ (N–O) band by 30 to 50 cm⁻¹ confirms the coordination through nitrogen of the oximino group⁶. In the VO^{II} and UO₂^{II} complexes, bands at 960 (V=O), 930 (U=O)⁷ and 450, 560 cm⁻¹ (M–O) were observed. In the Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV} complexes, the NH stretching frequency does not appear indicating deprotonation of NH groups and their replacement by the metal. These conclusions are corroborated by a comparison of the ketoamide bands in the spectra of the resin and the complexes. The ketoamide bands (1 475 and 1 450 cm⁻¹) have been found to be blue-shifted⁸ at 1 285 cm⁻¹, which supports coordination through the nitrogen atom. A band of medium intensity at 450 cm⁻¹ has been assigned to ν_{M-N} mode.

Magnetic moment and electronic spectra: The magnetic moment of the Cu^{II} complex is 1.72 B.M. which is close to the value expected for a square-planar geometry. The reflectance spectrum shows two bands at 16 129 and 23 255 cm⁻¹. The band at 16 129 cm⁻¹ is assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ transition. The position of this band is in the range generally observed for planar Cu^{II} complexes. The high energy band at 23 255 cm⁻¹ is due to symmetry forbidden ligand-metal charge transfer transition⁹. The Ni^{II} complex shows a magnetic moment of 3.10 B.M. which is close to the range (2.8–3.3 B.M.) required for octahedral stereochemistry. The reflectance spectrum of the Ni^{II} complex exhibits three bands at 9 300, 15 500 and 21 500 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ${}^2A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively, considering an octahedral symmetry. The structure is further confirmed by the ratio ν_2/ν_1 which is 1.67, close to the value expected for octahedral structure¹⁰. The Co^{II} complex has a magnetic moment of 5.12 B.M. indicating it to be high-spin with three unpaired electrons and having octahedral stereochemistry¹¹. The reflectance spectrum of the Co^{II} complex exhibits three bands at 8 772, 16 260 and

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
		C	H	N	M
<i>o</i> -HAcOUF	Brown	54.63 (56.17)	5.45 (5.53)	17.53 (17.87)	—
[Cu(<i>o</i> -HAcOUF) ₂] _n	Green	54.10 (54.15)	4.90 (4.92)	11.44 (11.48)	13.00 (13.03)
[Ni(<i>o</i> -HAcOUF) ₂ ·2H ₂ O] _n	Greenish yellow	50.91 (50.95)	4.62 (4.63)	10.78 (10.80)	11.20 (11.12)
[Co(<i>o</i> -HAcOUF) ₂ ·2H ₂ O] _n	Brown	50.85 (50.87)	4.58 (4.62)	10.74 (10.79)	11.32 (11.35)
[Zn(<i>o</i> -HAcOUF) ₂] _n	Grey	53.90 (53.94)	4.88 (4.90)	11.41 (11.44)	13.32 (13.36)
[Mn(<i>o</i> -HAcOUF) ₂ ·2H ₂ O] _n	Black	51.24 (51.27)	4.62 (4.66)	10.81 (10.87)	10.65 (10.67)
[VO(<i>o</i> -HAcOUF) ₂ ·2H ₂ O] _n	Green	51.83 (51.87)	4.70 (4.71)	11.00 (11.00)	13.14 (13.16)
[UO ₂ (<i>o</i> -HAcOUF) ₂] _n	Brick red	39.81 (39.87)	3.60 (3.62)	8.42 (8.46)	35.78 (35.96)
[Ti(<i>o</i> -HAcOUF) ₂] _n	Yellowish white	55.90 (55.94)	5.06 (5.08)	11.84 (11.86)	10.14 (10.15)
[Zr(<i>o</i> -HAcOUF) ₂] _n	Yellow	55.85 (55.89)	4.88 (4.90)	13.70 (13.73)	5.84 (5.87)

and 19 802 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively, considering an octahedral geometry¹². The magnetic moment of 5.12 B.M. for Mn^{II} complex is lower than the spin-only value (5.92 B.M.) which may be due to partial oxidation of Mn^{II} to Mn^{III} during synthesis, and suggests octahedral structure¹³. The reflectance spectrum of the Mn^{II} complex exhibits three bands at 16 260, 18 975 and 22 988 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to the ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}({}^4G)$, ${}^4A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}({}^4G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g({}^4G)$ transitions respectively, considering an octahedral symmetry. The magnetic moment of the VO^{II} complex is 1.55 B.M. normally observed for octahedral symmetry. The reflectance spectrum of the VO^{II} complex exhibits three bands at 11 062, 16 992 and 24 570 cm^{-1} corresponding to the ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$ transitions respectively for an octahedral structure. The UO_2^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes are found to be diamagnetic as expected. The Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV} complexes possess magnetic moments 0.11 and 0.15 B.M. respectively, indicating their diamagnetic nature. The reflectance spectra of the Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV} complexes show a single charge transfer band¹⁴ at 27 272 and 24 691 cm^{-1} respectively, which is in accord with their $(n-1)d^0ns^0$ electronic configuration.

Thermal study: From the loss of weight at different temperatures for *o*-HAcOUF and its com-

plexes, the order of thermal stability¹⁵ has been found to be $o\text{-HAcOUF} > \text{Ni}^{II} > \text{Zn}^{II} > \text{Mn}^{II} > \text{Co}^{II} > \text{Cu}^{II} > \text{Ti}^{IV} > \text{UO}_2^{II} > \text{Zr}^{IV} > \text{VO}^{II}$. The removal of water above 150° in case of the Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Mn^{II} and VO^{II} complexes indicates the presence of coordinated water molecules¹⁶.

From the above study and the structure of resin discussed earlier¹⁷, the structures (I) and (II) may be proposed for the complexes^{1,18}.

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References

1. M. M. PATEL and R. M. JOSHI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **21**, 637.
2. M. M. PATEL and R. MANAVALAN, *J. Macromol. Sci. Chem.*, 1983, **20**, 487.
3. FRENDBURG and ORTHNER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1922, **55**, 1949.
4. B. K. PATEL and M. M. PATEL, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990 **29**, 90.
5. K. NAKANISHI, "Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy", 2nd. ed., NaNkodo Co. Ltd., Tokyo, 1964, pp. 20, 30, 50.
6. R. BLINK and D. HADZI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 4536
7. S. K. MADAN and A. M. DONOHUE, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 1303; I. S. AHUJA and R. S. SINGH, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 561.
8. T. L. LANE, A. YAMAGUCHI, J. V. QUAGLIANO, J. A. RAYAN and S. MIZUSHIMA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 3824.
9. A. SYAMAL and K. S. KALE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, **16**, 46.
10. M. R. ROSENTHAL and T. M. SHEPHERD, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 840.
11. R. L. CARLIN, "Magnetochemistry", Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1986, p. 65.
12. A. B. P. LEVER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 2041.
13. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 611.
14. G. P. POKHARIYAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 416.
15. R. L. VOGES, C. V. PITTMAN and J. ELDER, *Macromolecules*, 1971, **4**, 302.
16. A. V. NIKOLAEV, V. A. LOGVINENKO and L. I. MAYACHINA, "Thermal Analysis", Academic, New York, 1969, Vol. 2, p. 779.
17. K. D. PATEL and M. M. PATEL, *Indian J. Technol.*, 1989, **27**, 541.
18. K. S. SIDDIQI, N. H. KHAN, R. I. KURESHV, S. TABASSUM and S. A. A. ZAIDI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 495.

(I)

where $M = \text{Cu}^{II}, \text{Ni}^{II}, \text{Co}^{II}, \text{Zn}^{II}, \text{Mn}^{II}, \text{VO}^{II}$ and UO_2^{II} ;
 X and $X' = \text{zero}$ when $M = \text{Cu}^{II}, \text{Zn}^{II}$ and UO_2^{II} ;
 X and $X' = \text{H}_2\text{O}$ when $M = \text{Ni}^{II}, \text{Co}^{II}$ and Mn^{II} ;
 $X = \text{O}$ and $X' = \text{H}_2\text{O}$ when $M = \text{VO}^{II}$.

(II)

where $M = \text{Ti}^{IV}$ and Zr^{IV}